

TIRZEPATIDE A NEW DRUG APPROACH IN DIABETES MANAGEMENT: A REVIEW

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ABSTRACT

Over 3,000 years ago, the ancient Egyptians discussed a condition that was type 1 diabetes. In ancient India, people discovered that they could use ants to test for diabetes by presented urine to them. If the ants came near to the urine, this was a sign that it contained high sugar. They names this condition madhumeha, which means honey urine. During 3rd century, Apollonius of Memphis called the term “diabetes. In the 5th century, people in India and China had work out that type 2 diabetes was common. In 1776 Matthew Dobson suggest that the urine of diabetic patient had sweet taste. In 1910 Sir Edward Albert Sharpey

Schafer confirmed that diabetes developed when there was a lack of particular chemical that produced by pancreas and he named it insulin. In 1921 Frederick Benting and Charles worked with two other scientists to purify insulin and produced the first treatment for diabetes. In 1936 sir harold Percival published research between type 1 and type 2 diabetes.

Type 1 -Diabetes is due to the genetic factors .The type 1 diabetes is a lifelong condition in which body does not produce enough insulin when the blood sugar levels is high. In the research of 2016 diabetes 5.8% of adult have diabetes in the country.

Type 2 -The type 2 diabetes is the most common form of diabetes The type 2 diabetes occurs when a person's body no longer respond to insulin correctly. This is called insulin resistance. In 2019, 37.3 millions peoples have diabetes and mostly type two.

This may 2022 FDA approval a drug TIRZEPATIDE (mounjaro). The medication is the first new diabetes medications. Tirzepatide is brand new type of medication approved for

treatment of type 2 diabetes. Tirzepatide is an injectable medication but it is not a form of insulin. In this article we discuss all the effect and side-effects of this new drug.

KEYWORDS: Tirzepatide, mounzaro, diabetes, insulin.

INRODUCTION

Our body uses and regulates glucose as a fuel with help of biochemical cycles taking place in body. when there is disability in the way of regulating and using glucose and continues for a long time this chronic condition results in too much circulation of sugar or glucose in the bloodstream which can be termed as Type 2 diabetes This can lead to fatal disorders of nervous, circulatory and immune systems. It also used to be called as adult-onset diabetes. It often develop too slowly and shows following symptoms

- Increased thirst
- Fatigue
- Blurred visions
- Frequent urination
- Increased hunger
- Unintended weight loss
- Frequent infections
- Darkened skin usually in armpits and neck

Primarily it can be the result of 2 problems

1. Poor interaction of cells present in muscles and liver with insulin as they don't take in enough glucose or they become insulin resistant.
2. The pancreas become unable to secrete enough insulin.

In May 2022 the FDA approved tirzepatide which comes under brand name mounjaro for adults living with Type 2 diabetes. Tirzepatide is an once a week injection but it's not an insulin which comes in six different strengths. To lower the risk of side effects it is prescribed to start with the lowest strength and gradually raise it (if needed). It is also called as a dual glucose-dependent insulinotropic polypeptide (GIP) and glucagon-like peptide-1 (GLP-1) receptor agonist. this is the first dual GIP/GLP-1 receptor agonist. Tirzepatide acts like incretins i.e. GIP and GLP-1, these are two hormones which is naturally synthesized and secreted by our body. These hormones are known as incretins.

MECHANISM

When we eat our body releases two incretins called as GIP and GLP-1 which tell our pancreas to release insulin and help us feel full and this is called as the incretin effect. It helps us to digest our food properly and keep the level of our blood sugar (glucose) stable. But for people with Type 2 diabetes, incretins doesn't work in a proper way. And tirzepatide mimics what GIP and GLP-1 do in the body. This helps in raising the amount of insulin that our body releases after meals and lowers blood sugar. Tirzepatide makes our body more sensitive to insulin. This helps our body to move sugar from the blood to our cells. In addition, tirzepatide prevents our liver from making more glucose and slow down the time taken to move food from our stomach to intestines. This helps in feeling fuller for longer period of time which can lead to weight loss. It can be injected beneath the skin of our belly, upper arm, or thigh. It is recommended to change the area of injecting with every dose to prevent skin irritation. It can be use any time of day with or without food.

CHEMICAL FORMULA - C225H348N48O68

MOLECULAR MASS - 4810.52

STRENGTHS

2.5 mg/0.5 mL

5 mg/0.5 mL

7.5 mg/0.5 mL

10 mg/0.5 mL

12.5 mg/0.5 mL

15 mg/0.5 mL

It is prescribed to start with the lowest strength i.e. 2.5 mg per week. After 4 weeks one can increase dose it can be raised up to 5 mg once a week. After that dose can be raised by an additional 2.5 mg every 4 weeks until our blood sugar of patient is well-controlled. The maximum dose which can be use is 15 mg once a week.

HALF LIFE - It is conjugated to a 20C fatty diacid that is attached to albumin to extend its half life to 5 days and to make it administrable once a week.

ABSORPTION – Tirzepatide takes 8 hours to 72 hours to reach in maximum plasma levels after subcutaneous injection. It has 80 percent absolute bioavailability after subcutaneous (SC) injection in thigh, arms or belly's subcutaneous tissue.

SIDE EFFECTS – it has following side effects

- Thyroid C-Cell tumor
- Pancreatitis
- Acute gallbladder disease

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